

SANSA NEWSLETTER

SANSA Newsletter 53

No. 53
JAN—MAR 2025

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LITERATURE

World Arachnid Catalog: cites 7806 articles, not all are yet available as PDF (work in progress).

World Spider Catalog: 18,179 articles are in the system as PDFs, this corresponds to unbelievable 100 % of the cited bibliography.

NEW SPECIES DESCRIBED PER YEAR

WSC: 885 new spider species have been described in 2024 (blue line). This is one of the highest numbers we ever had. Moreover, most years after 2008 are above the 33-years-average of 690 new species per year (green line). The number of publications needed to describe these species increased from 200 publications to nearly 600 in the period illustrated here (dark orange line).

2024 WAS A VERY GOOD YEAR!

Although we are only a few professional arachnologists employed in South Africa, we are grateful for the help of our good friends from abroad, who assist in adding new data on South African arachnids every year. A total of 53 articles have been published dealing with South African arachnids, adding three new genera and 22 species to our Spider National List, bringing it to a total of **2336**.

1. NEW GENERA:

SALTICIDAE

Foordus Azarkina, 2024
Helafricanus Wesolowska, 1986
Heliocapensis Wesolowska, 1986
Trapezocephalus Berland & Millot, 1910

TRACHELIDAE

Coronarachne Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius Haddad & Lyle, 2024

2. NEW SPECIES:

MACROBUNIDAE

Chumma foordi Marusik & Haddad, 2024

SALTICIDAE

Baryphas parvulus Haddad & Vickers, 2024
Foordus stefani Azarkina, 2024
Icius jacksoni Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024
Menemerus foordi Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024
Natta triguttata Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

TRACHELIDAE

Coronarachne denticulata Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne penicillus Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne setosa Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne unigena Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne neethlingi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea amatola Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea gladius Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius bosselaersi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius felis Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius peterwebbi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius tyume Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius umbella Haddad & Lyle, 2024

ZODARIIDAE

Asceua foordi Jocqué & Henrard, 2024

PSEUDOSCORPIONES, GEOGARYPIDAE

Afrogarypus foordi Neethling & Harm, 2024

3. FIRST RECORDS:

Theridion bicruciatum Roewer, 1961
Thomisus ghesquierei Lessert, 1943

4. NEW PHOTO IDENTIFICATION GUIDE:

The Zodariidae of South Africa. SANSa Photo Identification Guide part 1 (A-G)

5. PUBLISHED CHECKLISTS:

Spiders from Eucalyptus plantations
 Garden Route National Park (245 spp.)
 Golden Gate Highlands National Park (170 spp.)
 Karoo National Park (148 spp.)
 Phinda Sand Forest (64 spp.)
 Pretoria National Botanical Garden (152 spp.)
 Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (245 spp.)
 South African Cape Floristic Kingdom (960 spp.)
 Soutpansberg Mountain (585 spp.)
 Table Mountain National Park (261 spp.)

6. NEW INFORMATION ON SPECIES

Amoxenus amphalodes Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980
Artema atlanta Walckenaer, 1837
 Bominae genera (quick key)
Chresiona invalida (Simon, 1898)
Coryssiphus cinerascens Simon, 1903 (redescription)
Coryssiphus praeustus Simon, 1903 (redescription)
Eusparassus schoemanae Moradmand, 2013
Gephyrota glauca (Jézéquel, 1966)
Hermippus septemguttatus Lawrence, 1942 (1st male)
Hirriusa arenacea (Lawrence, 1927)
Neoscona rufipalpis (Lucas, 1858)
Olios correvoni nigrifrons Lawrence, 1928
Steatoda capensis Hann, 1990
Suemus punctatus Lawrence, 1938
Thomisus citrinellus Simon, 1875
Thomisus daradioides Simon, 1890
Thomisus stenningi Pocock, 1900
Uroctea quinquenotata Simon, 1910

7. SANSa NEWSLETTER

1. DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., BOOYSEN R., LOTZ L. & PATON J. 2024. *SANSa Newsletter* 49: 1–34..
2. DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., BOOYSEN R., LOTZ L. & PATON, J. 2024. *SANSa Newsletter* 50: 1–37.
3. DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., BOOYSEN R., LOTZ L. & PATON J. 2024. *SANSa Newsletter* 51: 1–35.
4. DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., BOOYSEN R., LOTZ L. & PATON J. 2024. *SANSa Newsletter* 52: 1– 44.

8. AFRAS COLLOQUIUM

Key note: DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2024. *SANSa* after 27 years: The present status of spiders in South Africa.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R., WIŚNIEWSKI K. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2024. The jumping spiders of Mozambique (Araneae: Salticidae). *Zootaxa* 5560(1): 1–92 DOI:10.11646/zootaxa.5560.1.1

ABSTRACT: Only 26 species of jumping spiders have been recorded from Mozambique to date. The present study is based on materials from four museum collections. Fourteen species are described as new to science: *Habrocestum mozambicum* sp. nov. (M, F), *Hyllus bisulcus* sp. nov. (M), *H. ornatus* sp. nov. (M, F), *H. simplex* sp. nov. (M), *H. tetensis* sp. nov. (F), *Langelurillus alius* sp. nov. (M), *L. pusillus* sp. nov. (M), *Langona spiralis* sp. nov. (F), *Phintella elegans* sp. nov. (F), *Rhene plumata* sp. nov. (M, F), *Thiratoscirtus clarus* sp. nov. (F), *T. gimoi* sp. nov. (F), *Thyene roeweri* sp. nov. (M) and *Vicirionessa spinosa* sp. nov. (M, F). Four new combinations are proposed: *Afraflacilla sengwaensis* (Wesołowska & Cumming, 2011) comb. nov., *Psenuc dentatus* (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2013) comb. nov. and *P. squamatus* (Haddad & Wesołowska, 2013) comb. nov. (all from *Pseudicius* Simon, 1885), and *Evarcha soricina* (Thorell, 1899) comb. nov. (from *Marpissa* C.L. Koch, 1846). The previously unknown sexes of two species, *Asemonea clara* Wesołowska & Haddad, 2013 (M) and *Thyene leighi* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (M), are described for the first time. The updated list of salticids from Mozambique contains 118 species, of which 78 are recorded from the country for the first time.

New for South Africa

Asemonea clara first male

Thyene leighi first female

NEW PUBLICATIONS

AZEVEDO G.H.F., HEDIN M. & MADDISON W.P. 2024. Phylogeny and biogeography of harmochirine jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 197(108109): 1–14. doi:10.1016/j.ympev.2024.108109

ABSTRACT: We use ultra conserved elements (UCE) and Sanger data to study the phylogeny, age, and biogeographical history of harmochirine jumping spiders, a group that includes the species-rich genus *Habronattus*, whose remarkable courtship has made it the focus of studies of behaviour, sexual selection, and diversification. We recovered 1947 UCE loci from 43 harmochirine taxa and 4 outgroups, yielding a core dataset of 193 UCES with at least 50 % occupancy. Concatenated likelihood and ASTRAL analyses confirmed the separation of harmochirines into two major clades, here designated the infratribes *Harmochirita* and *Pellenita*. Most are African or Eurasian with the notable exception of a clade of pellenites containing *Habronattus* and *Pellenattus* of the Americas and *Havaika* and *Hivanua* of the Pacific Islands. Biogeographical analysis using the DEC model favours a dispersal of the clade's ancestor from Eurasia to the Americas, from which *Havaika*'s ancestor dispersed to Hawaii and *Hivanua*'s ancestor to the Marquesas Islands. Divergence time analysis on 32 loci with 85 % occupancy, calibrated by fossils and island age, dates the dispersal to the Americas at approximately 4 to 6 million years ago. The explosive radiation of *Habronattus* perhaps began only about 4 mya. The phylogeny clarifies both the evolution of sexual traits (e.g., the terminal apophyses was enlarged in *Pellenes* and not subsequently lost) and the taxonomy. *Habronattus* is confirmed as monophyletic. *Pellenattus* is raised to the status of genus, and 13 species moved into it as new combinations. *Bianor stepposus* Logunov, 1991 is transferred to *Sibianor*, and *Pellenes bulawayoensis* Wesołowska, 1999 is transferred to *Neaetha*. A molecular clock rate estimate for spider UCES is presented and its utility to inform prior distributions is discussed.

Pellenes bulawayoensis Wesołowska, 1999 is transferred to *Neaetha bulawayoensis*. Credits: Vida vd Walt.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R. 2025. And they just keep coming: four new genera of dark sac spiders from southern Africa (Araneae, Trachelidae). *African Invertebrates* 66(1): 19–64 (2025) DOI: [10.3897/AfrInvertebr.66.13929](https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.66.13929)

ABSTRACT: As part of ongoing revisions of the Afrotropical Trachelidae, four new genera are described from southern Africa: *Foordana* gen. nov., with *F. distincta* sp. nov. from South Africa (Eastern Cape, Free State, KwaZulu-Natal and Western Cape) as the type species, *F. flavipoda* sp. nov. from the Free State, *F. kasouga* sp. nov. from the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal, and a fourth undescribed species from Zimbabwe; the monotypic *Mushimane* gen. nov., with *M. tswibilinki* sp. nov. from KwaZulu-Natal as the type species; *Namaquella* gen. nov., with *N. arida* sp. nov. from the Northern Cape as the type species and *N. samanthae* sp. nov. from the Western Cape; and *Rukuluk* gen. nov. from South Africa, with *R. gramineus* sp. nov. from the Northern Cape as the type species and a second undescribed species from KwaZulu-Natal known only from juveniles.

Foordana distincta

Namaquella arida
Photos by Ruan Booysen

NEW PHOTO GUIDE

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S., & LOTZ L. 2024. *The Zodariidae of South Africa. Part 2 (H-T)*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide. Version 1: 1–49. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14568995

Zodariids are wandering spiders and important components of the ground-dwelling spider assemblage in South Africa. The family is known from 90 genera and 1298 species (World Spider Catalog, 2024) and 23 genera and 98 species are listed from South Africa.

In *Zodariidae part 2* we discuss 14 genera and 26 species of which the species of three genera *Mallinella*, *Mastidiores* and *Microdiores*, still need to be identified and described for South Africa. **From pages 46–49 we provide a quick photo key to all 23 genera recorded from South Africa.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14568995>

NEW PUBLICATIONS

SHERWOOD D. 2024. Studies on spider nomenclature – I: miscellaneous notes on unrecognisable species, new synonyms, and untenable subspecies (Araneae: Araneomorphae). *The Indochina Entomologist* 1 (23): 189–235. <https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2024.01.23>

ABSTRACT: Miscellaneous notes on the nomenclature of spiders are presented, resultant are: 6 new synonyms; 7 subspecies raised to, and 2 restored to, species level; 40 taxa are proposed as *nomina dubia*; 1 subspecies is declared a *subspecies inquirenda*, and 112 species described based on juvenile type material are proposed as *species inquirendae*.

A **species inquirenda** is a species of doubtful identity that requires further investigation. This term is used when there's uncertainty about the species classification, and more research is needed to clarify its identity.

Immature species from South Africa listed as *species inquirendae*

1. *Clubiona sparassella* Strand, 1909
2. *Artoria lycosimorpha* Strand, 1909
3. *Philodromus thanatellus* Strand, 1909
4. *Tapinothelella laboriosa* Strand, 1909
5. *Scytodes constellata* Lawrence, 1938
6. *Leucauge fishoekensis* Strand, 1909
7. *Tetragnatha caffra* (Strand, 1909)
8. *Theridion albidorsum* Strand, 1909
9. *Theridion octoferum* Strand, 1909
10. *Xysticus simonstownensis* Strand, 1909

SANKARAN P.M., HADDAD C.R. & TRIPATHI R. 2025. A review of the ground spider genus *Trichothyse* Tucker, 1923 (Araneae, Gnaphosidae). *Zootaxa* 5583(1): 39–70. [doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5583.1.2](https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5583.1.2)

The genus *Trichothyse* Tucker, 1923 is presently represented by four southern African species, *T. africana* (Tucker, 1923), *T. hortensis* Tucker, 1923 and *T. subtropica* Lawrence, 1927, known only from their females, and *T. fontensis* Lawrence, 1928, known only from the male. In this paper, the genus is reviewed and the latter three species are redescribed. The previously unknown female of *T. fontensis* is described for the first time. The female of *Xerophaeus zuluensis* Lawrence, 1938 is redescribed, its previously unknown male is described for the first time, and the species is hereby transferred to *Trichothyse* as *T. zuluensis* (Lawrence, 1938) comb. nov. A new species known from both sexes, *T. karoo* Haddad & Sankaran sp. nov., is described from South Africa, and the hitherto unknown male of *T. jodhpurensis* (Gajbe, 1993) comb. nov. is described for the first time, together with a redescription of its female. Eleven species and one subspecies are transferred from *Poecilochroa* Westring, 1874 *sensu lato* to *Trichothyse*, two of which are of African distribution [*T. antennae* (Fage, 1929) comb. nov. and *T. pugnax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874) comb. nov.], nine that are distributed in the Palearctic Region [*T. furcata* (Simon, 1914) comb. nov., *T. golan* (Levy, 1999) comb. nov., *T. hamipalpis* (Kroneberg, 1875) comb. nov., *T. ilkerakkusi* (Coşar, Danişman & Marusik, 2024) comb. nov., *T. jodhpurensis* comb. nov., *T. loricata* (Kritscher, 1996) comb. nov., *T. perversa* (Simon, 1914) comb. nov., *T. poonaensis* (Tikader, 1982) comb. nov. and *T. senilis auspex* (Simon, 1878) comb. nov.], and one that has an extended distribution in both the Palearctic Region and Africa [*T. senilis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872) comb. nov.].

FIGURE 120. Distribution records of the known Afrotropical *Trichothyse* species.

Trichothyse hortensis

Trichothyse karoo

Trichothyse zuluensis

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R. 2025. Non-acarine arachnids in the Ndumo Game Reserve: celebrating 100 years of research. *African Journal of Wildlife Research* 55: 81–92.

ABSTRACT: The state of scientific research on the non-acarine arachnids of the Ndumo Game Reserve is presented and its status as a biodiversity hotspot is supported by the exceptionally rich diversity of spiders (573 spp.), pseudoscorpions (11 spp.), scorpions (8 spp.), harvestmen (6 spp.), solifuges (2 spp.) and whip spiders (1 sp.), totalling 601 spp. Aside from baseline biodiversity research, biological research on spiders has focused on microhabitat preferences, reproductive biology and competition in web-building spiders; dietary breath, spatiotemporal distribution and predatory behaviour of myrmecophagous, araneophagous and termitophagous spiders; mimicry in myrmecomorphic spiders; and the provision of information on the microhabitat preferences of a broad range of species. Ecological studies have investigated bark-, ground- and canopy-dwelling assemblages, while karyological and taxonomic studies have covered a broad range of spider, harvestmen and pseudoscorpion taxa. Future research should build on this foundation by continuing biological research on the broad range of species available, generating more information on assemblage differences between biotopes and over longer temporal scales, and utilizing spiders and potentially other arachnids as bioindicators of ecological change.

Sylligma ndumi a thomisid species described from Ndumo Game Reserve Credits: Peter Webb.

JUNGHANNS A., BILDE T., LUBIN Y. & UHL G. 2024. Facultative iteroparity in a semelparous social spider, *Stegodyphus dumicola* (Araneae: Eresidae). *Journal of Arachnology* 52: 23–25.

ABSTRACT: Organisms can optimize their reproductive success by differential resource allocation. When adult survival is low, investment of all resources into a single reproductive event can be beneficial, favouring a semelparous strategy. In the spider genus *Stegodyphus* Simon, 1873 (Eresidae), all species are considered semelparous, based on observations of ancestral subsocial species. However, derived social species show task differentiation and helping by non-reproducing females. This could facilitate a facultative iteroparous strategy by providing sufficient resources to meet the threshold for repeated reproduction. We investigated the reproductive behaviour of groups with single breeding females in the cooperative breeding *Stegodyphus dumicola* Pocock, 1898. We found that mothers can depart from a strictly semelparous lifestyle by producing more than one clutch. The facultative iteroparity in *S. dumicola* may enhance colony growth and survival, and act as a mechanism to maintain sociality.

Female *Stegodyphus dumicola* feeding. Credit: Aart Louw.

**ESSA
XXIV**

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8 – 11 July 2025 | University of the Free State, Bloemfontein

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The Evolution of the Light Bulb Spider

Ed Herbst (edherbst346@gmail.com)

Drawing by Marcel Terblanche 2019 of a trout leaping clear of the water trying to grab a long-jawed water spider

Historians agree that fly fishing for trout originated in the northern hemisphere where mayflies and caddis play a large role in trout diet. In the southern hemisphere, terrestrial insects such as ants and beetles play a far more important role for trout in our streams. Trout are ambush predators detecting prey by its movement and, in this regard, there is no more obvious prey than a spider with its eight legs and waterproof feet leaving little dimples in the water surface which reflect light.

Hunting spiders like the Wolf Spiders (Lycosidae) (Fig. 1) and Fish-eating spiders (*Nilus massajee*) (Fig. 2) are ubiquitous on the trout streams near Cape Town. The first person to tie a fly in attempt to imitate one was an expatriate Englishman, Mark Mackereth, some 60 years ago (Fig. 3).

Mark, a bass player by profession, had met his South African wife in London and decided to pursue his career here. He joined the Cape Town Symphony orchestra and the Cape Piscatorial Society (CPS) in 1961 and his Caribou Spider – made from caribou fur – was an instant success.

Mark Mackereth's and the parachute-style Caribou Spiders.

Mark was the originator of the first South African fly to imitate the Wolf Spider (Fig. 4). Unlike conventional floating flies which have the supporting feather at the eye of the hook tied vertically, Mark used what is called a 'parachute hackle' which is tied in horizontally. It was tied in a style which we call impressionistic because it could be taken by trout for several insects, such as a beetle.

The next step in the quest for a more realistic imitation of the Wolf spider came decades later when a young University of Stellenbosch student, Leonard Flemming wrote in *Piscator*, journal of the Cape Piscatorial Society (: I recall an incident while fishing a small Cape stream during the late season. I watched the pale figure of the trout glide to and fro in the current while I was tying a fly to my tippet. A movement to the right of the inlet caught my eye and almost instantly the trout leapt clear of the water and grabbed a long-jawed water spider - that was dangling by its silken thread from a streamside bush - in midair!'

Leonard's Wolf Spider was quite a complex tie and Peter Brigg tied a simpler version which was a huge success.

Peter Brigg, webmaster of the 'Call of the Stream' blog, tied a simpler version of Leonard Flemming's Wolf Spider imitation (Figs 5 & 6).

I had been experimenting, with some success, with a spider which used a body made of foam rubber and rubber legs. I then spotted a photo of *Nilus massajee* (Fig. 2) taken by the late Peter Webb in the outstanding book 'Field Guide to South African Spiders' by Professor Ansie Dippenaar Schoeman and realised I could replicate the light dimples by adding a tiny drop of UV light-cured resin to the tips of the rubber legs. (Fig 7).

This is work in progress as, at the time of writing the 'Light Bulb Spider' has yet to be tested. Orange is a colour that has proved particularly attractive to trout and I'm hoping the light reflected from the resin will also trigger a reaction from them.

For more see the Instagram of Ed Herbst

https://www.instagram.com/p/DffSxmiM7Kd/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link

More on the mysterious green grass lynx spider “*Oxyopes* sp. 3”

Aansie Dippenaar-Schoeman SANSA (Project Manager (Dippenaaransie@gmail.com))

The emerging field of conservation biogeography concerns species and distribution dynamics and how they relate to biodiversity conservation. Its main currency is valid species-level determinations and distribution data. The knowledge and insights from these data depend on whether the species are valid and whether clear diagnoses exist to identify the species.

South Africa has a remarkable diversity of spiders, with 2336 known species. However, numerous species are undescribed and already, 250 species have been identified as new waiting for formal description. The publishing process is slow, and this may take time with a shortage of taxonomists.

In the 1980s, Australia developed a formulaic naming system for undescribed plant species. This was universally adopted in Australia in the 1990s, and allowed, from 1999, the inclusion of these undescribed taxa in the legislated National and State threatened species lists (Chapman *et al*, 2022).

Similar systems are not available in South Africa. Identifying the known spider species from photographs only on citizen science apps such as iNaturalist is difficult. In most spider families, correct identification depends on the genital identification of adults, for which you need a microscope. Unfortunately, a very small proportion of spiders photographed on iNaturalist are sampled to confirm their identification. It is mainly a species with distinct outstanding characteristics that can be identified based only on morphological characters.

Given the number of spiders sampled during the South African National Survey (SANSA) and photographs received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012, 2015), we implemented a system to keep track of “new species.” To solve this problem in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA), a species number is assigned to the genus. This enables us to locate the specimens later in the collection.

Only three genera of the family Oxyopidae are known from South Africa, but they are abundant, and large numbers were sampled. Many *Oxyopes* species were described from African countries between 1863 and 1938. Before any new species can be described it need to be compared with known species. It was an enormous task to eventually name 26 *Oxyopes* species presently recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). However, many remain unnamed.

While trying to identify all the members of *Oxyopes*, one species stands out by its bright green color with white bands over the body. It was sampled for the first time from *Vachellia tortilis* trees in the Limpopo Province in 1970. It was tentatively labeled as “*Oxyopes* sp. 3” when accessioned in the NCA. As part of the SANSA Virtual Museum, specimens photographed from various localities throughout South Africa were received, and some are shown in Fig. 1. Unfortunately, the species was first uncorrectly identified as *Oxyopes affinis* by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014).

On iNaturalist, there are over 10,000 images of *Oxyopes* specimens from all over the world. Of all the entries, only 10 records of *Oxyopes* sp. 3 were found, all from Namibia, South Africa, and Zimbabwe.

Diagnostic characters: Size: TL female and male 5-6 mm. The carapace is bright green with white longitudinal stripes over the carapace and abdomen. The eye region frequently bears reddish setae. The abdomen is short, oval, and pointed to the rear. Legs are the same colour as the carapace (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. *Oxyopes* sp. 3 sampled from various localities in South Africa.

DISTRUBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia (iNaturalist); South Africa (SANSa, iNaturalist); Zimbabwe (iNaturalist).

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Specimens sampled during SANSa surveys housed in the NCA (Fig. 2). **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bloemfontein, Free State Nat Bot Garden (-29.11, 26.22); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Irene (-25.89, 28.23); Kameeldrift (-25.66, 28.32); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (25.77, 28.30); Dinokeng (-25.4, 28.380); Hamman-skraal (-25.41, 28.27). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mpushini, Dlinza Forest (-29.63, 30.48); Kloof, Royal Natal National Park-Drakensberg Mts. (-28.73, 28.92). **Limpopo:** Goro Game Ranch (-22.99, 29.43); Lephalale/ Ellisras (-27.71, 23.32); Kampersrus (-24.48, 30.83); Dendron (-23.38, 29.33); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.12). **Mpumalanga:** Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14). **North West:** Potchefstroom (-26.70, 27.090); Rustenburg (-33.97, 18.934). **Western Cape:** Gondwana Game Reserve (-34.07, 21.9).

iNaturalist: Kilowern Farm Rhodes (-30.866, 27.94); Sabie Sand (-25.10, 30.78); Plettenberg Bay (-34.06, 23.36); Kenton-on-Sea (-33.68, 26.67); Sendelingsdrif (-28.13, 16.90).

LIFESTYLE

The species is a free-living plant dweller sampled by beating and sweeping vegetation. It was sampled from various tree species, the grass and herb layer, fynbos, and thicket. The species was sampled during surveys such as Addo National Elephant National Park (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2020; Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022); Gondwana Private Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck, 2023) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa *et al.*, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Due to climate change and habitat neglect, we need to do everything we can to protect known and unknown species that remain, and to do that, we need information about all species, even those that are still undescribed. We need to give them names and adequately communicate about them to be able to add them to conservation legislation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank Allen Jones, Peter Webb, Linda Wiese and Jolandie Buck for sharing their photographs.

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Observations of the African crab spider *Geraesta congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The crab spider *Geraesta congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) is endemic to Africa and was described as *Stephanopis congoensis* from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It was first recorded in South Africa in 2010, and it is known from the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, and Mpumalanga, South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described based on photographs of live specimens, and notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Geraesta* Simon, 1889 comprises six species and is restricted to the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The first two African species were found to be misplaced in the genus *Stephanopis* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869, and Benjamin (2011) transferred them both to *Geraesta*. The African species of *Geraesta* were revised by Benjamin (2015), and he recognized six species, with only *G. congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) from South Africa.

Geraesta congoensis was described as *Stephanopis congoensis* from the Democratic Republic of Congo. The species was reported for the first time in South Africa in 2010 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). Since then, specimens have been sampled from four provinces during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on colour variations. Updated notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

Specimens collected during SANSA are deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. As part of SANSA, photographs were requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Geraesta congoensis (Lessert, 1943)

Stephanopis congoensis Lessert, 1943: 333 Figs 6–8

Geraesta congoensis Benjamin, 2015: 313; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 239; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1051; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 32, 31.

Description: Size female total length 5–6 mm. Carapace almost as wide as long (Fig. 1); eyes in two recurved rows on small tubercles; anterior lateral eyes largest (Figs 3 & 4). In the adult live specimens, the carapace is brown with a paler triangular median band (Fig. 4); the integument densely covered by cream curly setae gives it a mottled appearance (Figs 3 & 4). Abdomen round; abdominal tubercles distinct to absent; abdomen dorsum colour and patterns vary from pale green (Fig. 5) to green bordered by a wide yellowish band (Figs 1 & 15); to green with dark paired spots (Figs 15–16). Some specimens without green markings. In both Lessert (1943) and Benjamin (2015) no mention is made of the green colour.

Figure 1–2. *Geraesta congoensis* 1. Female. 2. Immature male both collected in November 2017 from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–9. *Geraesta congoensis*. 3. Eye pattern anterior view. 4. Carapace dorsal view. 5. Juvenile habitus dorsal view. 6–7. Male palp. 8–9. Epigyne. Credits: 3–5. Peter Webb. 6 & 9. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 7–8. After Lessert (1943).

Leg formula 1243. Legs I and II are the same colour as the carapace; legs III and IV banded femora III and IV are translucent with narrow dark bands medially (Figs 1, 14, 16); tibiae and metatarsi I and II with 4-6 and 5-6 pairs of macro-setae respectively. Epigynum: broad medium spectrum, spermathecal orifices oval pits (Figs 8 & 9). Male. Size: TL 6.5. Carapace pale brown while abdomen varies between yellow brown to green with dark spots. Leg I and II are dark brown; legs III and IV banded (Fig. 2). Abdomen dorsum variable from green with dark spots (Figs 2 & 14) to brown (Figs 12 & 18). Palp with embolus winding once around the tegulum; a single tibial apophysis present (Figs 6 & 7).

Figures 10–12. *Geraesta congoensis*. 10. Female line drawing habitus. 11. Male dorsal habitus in alcohol. 12. Male dorsal view from Hoedspruit. Credits: 10. After Lessert (1943). 11. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 12. Wynand Uys.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: This genus is endemic to Africa and is now known from Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); East London (-33.01, 27.9). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Fanie’s Island (-28.1, 32.45); Giant’s Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Scottburgh (-30.28, 30.75); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Kloof, Durban (-29.78, 30.83); Westville (-29.82, 30.92); Wartburg (-29.43, 30.57). **Limpopo:** Penge (-24.38, 30.29); Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.578, 30.809); Hoedspruit (-24.35, 30.95). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke’s Luck (-25.09, 30.81).

Figures 13–16. *Geraesta congoensis* showing the colour variations. 13. Female from Kloof (Peter Webb). 14. Male from Hoedspruit (Wynand Uys). 15. Female abdomen (Peter Webb). 16. Male abdomen (Peter Webb).

iNaturalist records from: Cumberland Nature Reserve, Wartburg, KZN, Westville, Mbombela, Tembe, Kwangwanasie.

LIFESTYLE

Geraesta congoensis is a rare plant-dweller that is more commonly found on shrubs and herbs but occasionally also sampled from tree canopies. With their green colour they are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. It has been sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket, and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION STATUS

During SANSA surveys, the species have been sampled from the following reserves: Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve; Hluhluwe Nature Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010). The species has a wide distribution and listed as of Least Concern. No conservation actions are recommended.

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Figures 17-19. *Geraesta congoensis*. 17. Male from Hoedspruit with green abdomen. 18. Male from Hoedspruit with brown abdomen. 19. Female from Hoedspruit with green abdomen. Credits: 17 & 18. Wynand Uys. 19. Peter Webb.

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More on the litter crab spider *Borboropactus silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The litter crab spider *Borboropactus silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938) is endemic to South Africa and was described as *Regillus silvicola* from Port Shepstone, KwaZulu-Natal. It is now known from the Eastern Cape, Limpopo and several localities in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The general morphology of the species is noted based on photographs of live specimens. Notes on their behaviour updated distributional records, and their conservation status in South Africa are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

Numerous members of Thomisidae have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), including several *Borboropactus* specimens. The genus is recognized by its dark brown to grey bodies and legs, the strong front pair of legs with tibiae and metatarsi thick bearing a double row of strong setae. *Borboropactus* is also known for the presence of a specialized sensory region on the dorsal surface of the tarsi (Benjamin, 2011).

Borboropactus Simon, 1884 is represented by 19 species from the Oriental and Afrotropical regions (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Simon (1895) listed the genus in the Thomisidae and synonymized his *Borboropactus* Simon, 1884, with *Regillus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1884. However, *Regillus* was preoccupied and *Borboropactus* was revalidated. Wunderlich (2004) discovered members of the genus in amber and transferred the genus to Borboropactidae but that elevation was rejected by Benjamin *et al.* (2008). Benjamin (2011), using molecular data, placed *Borboropactus* within Thomisidae, sister to *Geraesta* Simon, 1889.

Eight of the *Borboropactus* species are African endemics, and three species, *B. australis* (Lawrence, 1937), *B. silvicola* (Lawrence, 1938), and *B. squalidus* Simon, 1884 are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

Borboropactus silvicola was described in 1938 from Port Shepstone, KwaZulu-Natal. Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2010) listed five new localities records, and Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2020) added 16 more. The morphology based on live specimens is discussed, and notes on their behaviour, conservation status and distribution are provided.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Requests were also made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and photographs of *B. silvicola* have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 1. *Borboropactus silvicola* female from Leggalameetse Nature Reserve, Limpopo province. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 2–9. *Borboropactus silvicola*. 2. Female habitus dorsal view. 3. Female ventral view. 4–6. Epigyne. 7–9. Male palp. Credits: 2, 3, 4–5, 7. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6, 8–9. After Lawrence (1938).

TAXONOMY

Borboropactus silvicola (Lawrence, 1938)

Regillus silvicolus Lawrence, 1938: 488

Borboropactus silvicola Roewer, 1955: 752; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023: 236; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1009; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 15, 13.

Description: Size female 7–8 mm, male 6–7 mm. Carapace dark brown, covered with dense whitish curled setae (Fig. 10) absent from the median area; longer clavate setae present on the posterior border and in the eye region (Figs 1 & 11). The carapace is narrower in the eye region (Figs 1 & 10); the fovea is longitudinal. Eyes in two rows; anterior row slightly pro-curved, posterior row very slightly recurved (Fig. 11); anterior medians larger than anterior laterals; median ocular area as wide behind than in front, longer than wide. Legs same colour as carapace with front legs directed to the front and not sideways; femora thick and inflated; tibiae and metatarsi I and II thick; with long macro setae in a double row below (Figs 2–3); legs covered by short clavate setae. Abdomen triangular, broadening towards the back; dorsally brown, without patterns; laterally paler; integument coriaceous; covered with dense, short, white clavate hairs with sparse, longer clavate setae scattered in between (Fig. 12). Epigyne: epigynal plate resembles a keyhole (Figs 4–6). Palp with a rudimentary retro tibial apophysis (Figs 7–9).

DISTRUBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Dwesa Nature Reserve (-32.27, 28.87); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.31, 29.96); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.62, 29.49); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Dlinza forest (-28.89, 31.45); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Westville (-29.82, 30.92). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Entabeni State Forest (-23.01, 30.23); Tzaneen Debengi waterfall (-23.83, 30.15). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

No photographs of *Borboropactus silvicola* on iNaturalist.

Figures 10–12. *Borboropactus silvicola* female. 10. Carapace dorsal view. 11. Eye pattern anterior view. 12. Abdomen dorsal view. Credits: Peter Webb.

LIFESTYLE

Borboropactus silvicola is a free-living ground dweller. They are usually found in leaf litter and blend in with their surroundings with their mottled colouration and general appearance. Due to the clavate setae covering their body, specimens are frequently covered with mud, and sand particles sometimes adhere to the setae.

Although they were sampled from four provinces in South Africa (Fig. 13), they are not common, and most of the specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys have been sampled from pitfall traps from the Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Forest Biomes. In the Mkambathi Nature Reserve in the Eastern Cape (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011) and Mariepskop in Mpumalanga (Taylor, 2020) the species was sampled during a yearlong survey. In the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), the second author (PW) sampled the species from decaying leaf litter in damp areas (Fig. 13). Only two specimens were listed on iNaturalist.

Figure 13. Peter Webb in the area where the species were sampled in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS

It is presently known from four South African provinces and protected in seven protected areas. There are no known threats and is listed as Least Concern.

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More on the crab spider *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The rare, crowned crab spider *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895, is an African endemic species that was described from Sierra Leone, West Africa, based on an immature specimen. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on live specimens with notes on their behaviour, conservation status and distribution in South Africa.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Thomisidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). *Smodicinus coroniger* Simon, 1895 was recognized by its modified carapace, which is highly elevated to form a crest (Fig. 1).

Smodicinus Simon, 1895 is monotypic and known only from Africa. The type-species *Smodicinus coroniger* was described from Sierra Leone, West Africa, based on immature specimens. A second species, *S. affinis*, from Zaïre, was added by Lessert (1943) based on a female. He stated that this species differs from *S. coroniger* in the shape of its crest. In a third paper, Jézéquel (1966) provided the first drawing of the male palp of *S. coroniger*. *Smodicinus coroniger* was the first time recorded from South Africa sampled from trees at Maasstroom in the Limpopo province.

The genus was revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) and specimens from six collections were examined. It was found the shape of the crest is variable. In *S. coroniger* the posterior pair of tubercles of the crest and genitalia resemble *S. affinis* and the species was recognized as a junior synonym of *S. coroniger*. In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) several more specimens sampled from the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal were listed. In this paper more information is added on their morphology, behaviour, conservation status and distribution.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Requests were also made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Smodicinus coroniger Simon, 1895

Smodicinus coroniger Simon, 1895a: 433; 1895b: 992
Jézéquel, 1966: 625; Dippenaar-Schoeman 1980: 339;
Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 4.

Description: **Size:** TL females and males 3–6 mm. The carapace is pale brown, infused with yellow, sometimes with white markings on the edge. The carapace is modified, it is highly elevated to form a crest that is flattened above with six-pointed tubercles; two tubercles are pointed posteriorly and four laterally (Figs 1 & 3). Eyes: both eye rows recurved; situated on small tubercles; laterals larger than medians; posterior lateral eyes smallest, situated nearer to posterior lateral eyes than to each other; median ocular quadrangle broader than long with the posterior lateral eyes situated on the posterior side and the anterior lateral eyes situated anteriorly (Figs 1 & 2).

Figures 1–3. *Smodicinus coroniger* female. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Figures 4–10. *Smodicinus coroniger*. 4-5. Female carapace dorsal view. 6. Female habitus dorsal view. 7. Female habitus ventral view. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 4, 6 & 7. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5 & 10. Lessert (1943). 8-9. Jézéquel (1966).

Chelicerae anteriorly flattened, bearing on the edge small tubercles, each provided with a seta which is directed forwards (Fig. 1). Clypeus slightly sloping forwards, provided with two pairs of primary setae; lateral sides of clypeus with a pair of anterior-directed projections. Sternum and mouthparts yellowish-brown. Abdomen ovoid, blackish, mottled with white or with distinct white markings (Fig. 5); ventrally with two white spots mediolaterally (Fig. 6); spinnerets and epigastric area sometimes encircled with white. Legs I and II brown, banded with white; longer and stronger; rest only slightly longer than III and IV, the femora each provided with one strong dorsal seta; femur I armed with two small tubercles bearing a seta on each. Legs with a single spine on dorsal femur III and IV, otherwise spineless. Epigynum as wide as long, with a depression medially, divided longitudinally by an indistinct septum (Fig. 9). Palp with coiled retro lateral apophysis (Figs 8 & 9).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ivory Coast (Lamto), Sierra Leone, South Africa and Zaire.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.01, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87). **Limpopo:** Alldays (-22.67, 29.10); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.65, 29.04); Maasstrom (Farm Al te ver) (-22.75, 28.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Syferkuil (-23.85, 29.712).

iNaturalist: No records from South Africa listed.

LIFESTYLE

Smodicinus coroniger is free-living plant-dwellers. According to Lessert (1943) they are myrmecomorphic imitating the tree ant *Cataulacus erinaceus* Stitz. During surveys mainly in the Savanna Biome *S. coroniger* was sampled while beating trees (Foord *et al.*, 2011). In the Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) it was sampled from *Burkea africana*. In the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) it was sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* and *V. xanthophloea* trees in the forests around the pans and Sand Forest. Males were sampled from November to March and females from October to January.

Figures 11–12. *Smodicinus coroniger* female. Credits: Brian Ashby

CONSERVATION STATUS

During SANSА surveys, the species have been sampled from three provinces and it is protected in the following reserves: Cwebe Nature Reserve; Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Mkuzi Game Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve; Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa *et al.*, 2010) and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank Vida van der Walt and Brian Ashby for their photographs.

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Observation on the six-eyed sand spider *Hexophthalma spatulatus* (Pocock, 1900) from South Africa (Araneae: Sicariidae)

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ABSTRACT: The six-eyed sand spider *Hexophthalma spatulatus* (Pocock, 1900) is a South African endemic that was described in 1900 as *Sicarius spatulatus* from Port Elizabeth in the Eastern Cape. They are free-living ground dwellers and one of the most distinctive features is their ability to blend into their sandy environment. The tufts of sickle-shaped setae on their abdomen and legs help in holding the sand covering in place. Based on photographs of live specimens, the general morphology of the species are discussed with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

Sicariidae specimens represented by two genera *Hexophthalma* and *Loxosceles* have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). *Hexophthalma* Karsch, 1879 is represented by eight species and four of the species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

They are free-living ground dwellers, known as the six-eyed sand spiders, and are usually covered in sand particles, making them cryptic against their background (Duncan *et al.*, 2007). They can stay motionless for long periods beneath the soil surface, waiting for prey (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

Hexophthalma spatulatus (Pocock, 1900) is a South African endemic species described in 1900 as *Sicarius spatulatus* from Port Elizabeth. In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) seven localities from two provinces were sited. The species has since been recorded from 18 localities in two provinces (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

The most remarkable characteristic of members of *Hexophthalma* is their cryptic appearance and behaviour. The dry soil particles adhere to special body setae bearing fine hair (Duncan *et al.*, 2007; Magalhaes *et al.*, 2017). Two types of body covering have been observed. Some species have a higher density of body setae with multiple rows of macrosetae on the lateral border of the carapace, prolateral setae on the femora, and abdomen giving them a 'dirtier' appearance compared to the 'cleaner' species. Observations showed that the 'dirtier' species are more cryptic and tend to remain motionless on the soil, while the 'cleaner' species cover themselves with sand particles disappearing below the surface (Duncan *et al.*, 2007).

Hexophthalma spatulatus is one of the 'dirtier' species and is covered with a dense layer of sand particles (Figs 1 & 2). In this paper, the general morphology of the species is discussed based on observations of live specimens, with notes on their colour variation, general behaviour, conservation status, and distribution in South Africa.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Photographs were also requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum, and photographs of *Hexophthalma spatulatus* from several localities have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Figures 1–2. *Hexophthalma spatulatus*. 1. Female from Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve. 2. Female from Addo Elephant National Park. Credits: 1. Joy Paton. 2. Linda Wiese.

Figures 3–10. *Hexophthalma spatulatus*. 3. Male body dorsal view. 4. Eye pattern. 5. Setae on abdomen. 6. Femora enlarged scoop-shaped seta. 7–8. Male palp. 9–10. Spermathecae. Credits: 3–5, 8–9. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6–7, 10. After Magalhães *et al.*, 2013.

TAXONOMY

Hexophthalma spatulata (Pocock, 1900)

Sicarius spatulatus Pocock, 1900: 321 (mf); Newlands, 1986: 56; Lotz, 2012: 10.

Hexophthalma spatulata Magalhães, Brescovit & Santos 2017: 853; Lotz, 2018: 14; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 10; 2023: 360.

Diagnosis: Size: Total length 8–9 mm. Carapace flat, as wide as long; narrower in eye region; integument hard, coriaceous; six eyes in two rows, in three diads (Fig. 4). Abdomen markedly depressed, clothed in sickle-shaped curved setae (Figs 3–5). Legs laterigrade; stout with two claws with several serrated bristles born on a small onychium; legs clothed in sickle-shaped setae; femora with enlarged scoop-shaped setae (Fig. 6) dorsally raised on a slight mound. Haplogyne spiders; male embolus with a broad, blunt apex (Figs 7 & 8); female spermathecae consist of numerous copulatory tubes; opening directly into epigastric furrow (Figs 9 & 10). Males resemble females, but their legs are longer, spanning up to 30 mm.

Colour variation: Specimens preserved in alcohol are very dark grey (Fig. 11). *Hexophthalma spatulatus* is one of the 'dirtier' species and the colour of specimens photographed depends on the colour of the sand particles adhering to their bodies (Figs 2 & 12).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Caledon (-32.4, 19.43); Piketberg (-32.90, 18.75); Swellendam, Tradouws Pass (-33.95, 20.7); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Van der Kemps Kloof (-33.876, 25.454); Kammanasie Nature Reserve (-33.66, 23.12); N of Mosselbay (-34.010, 22.056); Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve (-33.583, 23.438)*; Bereaville Riviersonder end Nature Reserve (-34.039, 19.493)*; Gondwana Game Reserve SE Herbertsdale (-34.07, 21.9); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5)*; Paternoster (-32.81, 17.89)*

* From iNaturalist

LIFESTYLE

Hexophthalma spatula has been sampled by hand and in pitfall traps, mainly from the Fynbos and Thicket Biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024) in the Eastern and Western Cape. One of their most distinctive features is their remarkable ability to blend into their sandy environments. In their natural habitat, they face threats from larger predators, including birds, reptiles, and mammals. As predators they play a critical role in keeping the insect and arachnid populations in check, ensuring a balanced ecosystem.

Hexophthalma spatula, with its dense layer of setae, catches a thick layer of soil particles to the cuticle (Fig. 11). This helps to conceal the spider, resulting in them remaining motionless on the soil surface, moving only when molested (Duncan *et al.*, 2007). During mating the males are more active and aggressive, roaming around searching for a mate.

Figures 11–12. *Hexophthalma spatulatus* female. 11. Alcohol material. 12. Live female from Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve. Credits: 11. ASD. 12. Joy Paton.

Simon (1899) first noted their unusual cup-like egg cocoon, covered with sand, and usually attached to the substrate. Information on the burying behaviour of members of *Hexophthalma* appears in Reiskind (1965), while Levi (1967) reported on their predatory and sexual behaviour and Levi & Levi (1969) on their sexual behaviour and the construction of the egg cocoon.

Species of *Hexophthalma* have also raised interest because of their supposed medical importance. Laboratory studies in South Africa by Newlands (1982), Newlands & Atkinson (1988) and Van Asweger et al., (1997) have shown that *Hexophthalma* bites cause severe ulcerating lesions and death in laboratory animals. Bites by *Hexophthalma* spp. are uncommon and according to Müller et al. (2012) clinical evidence is inconclusive.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution it is known from both sexes and is listed as Least Concern. The species is protected in Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2020); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Kammanasie Nature Reserve; Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve; Bereaville Riviersonder end Nature Reserve and Gondwana Game Reserve.

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Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964 one of the typical grassland spider species from South Africa revisited (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel 1964 is a typical grassland species with a wide distribution. It is known from the Ivory Coast in the Afrotropical Region to South Africa in the south. It is presently known from eight provinces in South Africa. The female, with her characteristic decorated abdomen, is easily recognized. More information on its morphology, lifestyle, distribution, and conservation status is provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, reduced orb-web, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Runcinia* Simon, 1875, is represented by 27 species, of which 12 occur in Africa and eight are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) revised the genus, and they were found to be common grass dwellers. Large numbers were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964 is an African endemic species described from a subadult female from the Ivory Coast in 1964. Blandin (1972) described the male and female. The genus was the first time recorded from South Africa and Zimbabwe in 1980 from 12 localities (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980). In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) the species was reported from 38 localities. The species is now widespread throughout South Africa and is recorded in all the provinces except the Northern Cape.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Photographs were also requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum, and photographs of *R. erythrina* were received from several localities (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964: 1123(J); Blandin, 1972: 1281–1285(MF); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 312; 1983: 43; 2023: 253; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1044–1045; 2013: 79–81; 2020: 53–54.

Description: Medium-sized (female 4–8 mm (Fig. 1); male 3–4 mm (Fig. 2). Female: Carapace fawn with reddish-brown tint with lateral bands; as wide as long or slightly longer; flattened above;

Figures 1–2. *Runcinia erythrina*. 1. Female dorsal views from Irene. 2. Male dorsal views from Irene. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–13. *Runcinia erythrina*. 3. Female habitus line drawing, 4–5. Female abdomens. 6. Epigyne. 7. Spermatheca. 8–10. Male habitus. 11. Male palp. 12. Abdominal setae. 13. Eye pattern. Credits: 3, 8. After Blandin (1972). 4–5, 9–10, 13. Peter Webb. 6–7, 11–12. After Dippenaar-Schoeman, (1980).

anterior margin straight, posterior margin concave; surface clothed with numerous irregularly spaced, short spiniform setae. Eyes in two rows; anterior row on the frontal slope, posterior row on the dorsal side; anterior margin is straight medially, with two low tubercles (carinae) on each side; lateral eye larger than median eyes (Fig. 13). Abdomen creamy with a distinct reddish-brown pattern that varies slightly between specimens (Figs 3–5); oval longer than wide; posteriorly rounded; with longitudinal striae following contour of abdomen with rows of dark setae (Fig. 12). Legs fawn; I and II longest; tibiae and metatarsi with strong, paired macrosetae (Fig. 17). Epigyne (Fig. 6). Male: Slenderer than females. Abdominal patterns less distinct or absent (Figs 8–10), with longer legs (Fig. 18). Palp with medium length retrolateral apophysis (Fig. 11).

Figures 14–15. *Runcinia erythrina* female on their egg sacs. Credits: 14–15. Allen Jones.

LIFESTYLE

Runcinia erythrina is a semi-sedentary spider and excels as an ambusher. With their elongated bodies and cryptic colouration, their bodies blend in with the grass. They move freely around on the grass and are mainly active during the day, waiting for prey. They have strong bodies and robust front legs that enable them to attack prey, sometimes larger than themselves (Fig. 17). They construct their egg sacs in grass inflorescences and cover the sac with pieces of grass (Figs 14–15). The males were collected in December, and the females from October to May.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021), Zimbabwe, Botswana (new record, Thamalakane river NCA) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: During the SANSa surveys they were mainly sample sweeping the grass and herb layer. The species has been sampled during surveys in the Grassland biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna biome (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2013; Foord *et al.*, 2011) and the Fynbos biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

In the SANSa database, they have been recorded from 50 localities (for all the localities, see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 53–54). They were sampled during several grassland surveys of which the following results have been published: Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2023); Golden Gate Highland National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023); Tembe Elephant

Figure 16. Map showing the distribution of *Runcinia erythrina* in South Africa.

Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2020); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024).

iNaturalist: Although the species seems to be widely distributed only two entries from Bedford and Paternoster are presently listed.

Figures 17–18. *Runcinia erythrina*. 17. Female on fynbos feeding. 18. Male showing the long legs. Credits: 17–18. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution it is known from both sexes and is listed as Least Concern. The species is protected in 19 reserves and national parks in South Africa.

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Spider assemblages associated with the umbrella thorn tree *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.) in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: A total of 112 spider species from 17 families were collected over three years from *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.) from two localities in the Limpopo and the KwaZulu-Natal provinces. From the farm Amsterdam near Dendron, 14 families represented by 68 species were sampled, and from the farm Vergeval near Pongola, 17 families and 79 species. Thirty species (26.5%) are recorded from both sites. The aim was to find out whether the same tree species host different spider communities.

Keywords: biodiversity, Savanna Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

Spiders occupy different field layers, such as the ground layer, grass and herb layer, and the tree layers, with web dwellers making their webs everywhere (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024). Information is available on spider association with the soil surface (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2002; Janion-Scheepers *et al.*, 2016) and grass layer (Haddad *et al.*, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2014), but a few papers were published on spiders associated with the tree layer in the savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several studies have investigated the habitat association of spiders to tree canopies. Tree species differ in their habitat characters and consequently support different spider assemblages (Southwood *et al.*, 1982, 2005). At the Nylsvley Nature Reserve in the Limpopo Province, spider assemblages were sampled from five tree species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009). Neethling & Haddad (2013) studied arboreal spider species from four tree species in the Free State, while Haddad (2016) reported on the spiders sampled from the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* from the Ndumo Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal. Several tree species were surveyed in the northern arid aspects of the Blouberg and Soutpansberg (Muelelwa *et al.*, 2010).

Another way to sample trees was to use a fogging apparatus. Spider assemblages were sampled fogging trees in orchards in agroecosystems such as avocado trees (*Persea americana*) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), macadamia nut trees (*Macadamia integrifolia*) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and pistachio trees (*Pistacea vera*) (Haddad *et al.*, 2005). From citrus trees, spiders were sampled by beating and active search (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1992; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1998). Ten spider families were sampled using corrugated paper traps in commercial pine plantations near Sabie in Mpumalanga (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988).

In this paper, the spider assemblages sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.), also known as umbrella thorn, are discussed. The spiders were sampled during a 5-year project to determine the effect of Dieldrin cover spraying to control the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978). The aim was to find out whether the same tree species host different spider communities.

Vachellia tortilis is a medium-to-large, canopied tree native to areas in Africa and the Middle East. It is a hardy, deciduous, drought-resistant, slow-growing umbrella-shaped tree that can be 4–15 m tall. It often has several trunks but is usually reduced to a small, wiry shrub less than 1 m tall under arid conditions (Fig. 1). The tree bears two types of thorns (Fig. 2) and bears abundant, fragrant, white to yellow puffball flowers from November to January (Fig. 3), followed by distinctive curled pods (Fig. 4).

Figures 1–4. *Vachellia tortilis*. 1. The trees chosen to sample. 2. Branch with the white thorns. 3. White to yellow, puffball flowers. 4. Distinctive curled seed pods. Credits: Peter Webb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area and period: The surveys were undertaken at two sites (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978).

1. Farm Amsterdam (23° 16'S; 29° 27'E), Soutpansberg district, ± 16 km NE of Dendron/ Mogwadi, Limpopo. Sampling took place between 1968 to 1970.
2. Farm Vergeval (27° 31' S; 31° 42' E), Ngotshe district, 11 km SSE of Pongola, KwaZulu-Natal. Sampling took place between 1967 to 1968.

Map showing the two sites 1. Farm Amsterdam, Dendron/Mogwadi. 2. Farm Vergeval, Pongola.

Sampling methods: Spiders were sampled using a beating tray and beating branches of the *V. tortilis* trees. Trees of approximately equal size and form were chosen randomly. Four branches on each tree were beaten 10 times, and the falling arthropods were caught on a square sheet measuring 0.8 m². The total catch from four trees (= 16 branches) constituted a sample (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978).

Voucher specimens: The spiders sampled were preserved in 70% ethanol. Sorting and identifications were done in Pretoria at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection division, where the voucher specimens were deposited.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 112 species, 69 genera, and 17 families have been collected from both sites (Table 3). The three most species-rich families are the Salticidae (25 spp.), followed by the Araneidae (24 spp.) and Thomisidae (23 spp.). Two families are represented by singletons.

Thirty species (26.5%) are recorded from both sites from 14 families. Three families, Deinopidae, Mimetidae, and Zodariidae, were only sampled from Pongola. Many specimens collected from the trees were immature.

DENDRON. Numbers present: A total of 68 species, 50 genera, and 14 families were recorded (Table 3). This was one of the first surveys undertaken in South Africa, and data was included in the review article of the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Family diversity: Of the 14 spider families collected from Dendron (Table 3), the two most species-rich families are the Salticidae (18 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (16 spp.) and Araneidae (12 spp.). Four families are represented by singletons.

PONGOLA. Numbers present: A total of 79 species, 53 genera, from 17 families, were recorded (Table 3). This was one of the first surveys undertaken in the KwaZulu-Natal, and data was included in the review article of the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Family diversity: Of the 17 spider families collected from Pongola (Tables 3), the three most species-rich families are the Araneidae (23 spp.) Thomisidae (18 spp.) and Salticidae (14 spp.). Nine families are represented by singletons.

NEW SPECIES

The voucher material is deposited in the NCA and is available for taxonomic research. So far five species sampled from *V. tortilis* were newly described (Table 1).

Table 1: Species newly described from *Vachellia tortilis* trees at Pongola and Dendron.

PONGOLA		
Trachelidae	<i>Coronarachne denticulata</i>	Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Thomisidae	<i>Pherecydes carinae</i>	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980
Thomisidae	<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i>	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980
Zodariidae	<i>Thaumastochilus termitomimus</i>	Jocqué, 1994
DENDRON/MOGWADI		
Salticidae	<i>Menemerus meridionalis</i>	Wesołowska, 1999

Table 2: Spider families, genera (G) and species (SP.) and % of total sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* trees at Pongola and Dendron.

FAMILY	G	SP	%	FAMILY	G	SP	%
ARANEIDAE	13	24	0	SALTICIDAE	19	25	22.3
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	2	4	3.6	SELENOPIIDAE	1	2	1.8
CLUBIONIDAE	1	3	2.7	SPARASSIDAE	2	2	1.8
DEINOPIDAE	2	2	1.8	TETRAGNATHIDAE	2	2	1.8
ERESIDAE	2	2	1.8	THERIDIIDAE	5	6	5.4
HERSILIIDAE	1	2	1.8	THOMISIDAE	12	23	20.5
MIMETIDAE	1	1	0.9	ULOBORIDAE	3	3	2.7
OXYOPIIDAE	3	7	6.3	ZODARIIDAE	1	1	0.9
PHILODROMIDAE	1	3	2.7	TOTAL	71	112	

SPECIES SAMPLED

The spiders sampled from *V. tortilis* trees are free-living plant dwellers and web dwellers. The plant dwellers 73 spp. (65.2%) are found on the bark, foliage, and flowers while the web dwellers 39 spp. (34.8%) use the tree branches to attach their webs. When inactive, they rest on the tree, usually the bark. Bark dwellers either live on the surface of the bark or in holes and cracks in or under the bark. They have a mottled appearance and are usually very well camouflaged, closely resembling pieces of bark. Their colour varies from greyish white to dark brown, and their bodies are frequently flattened or with knobs and spiny protuberances.

This survey confirmed that certain species can be considered typical tree dwellers. Some genera, like *Hersilia*, are only known from trees, but others are not so well known. In comparing the spider species collected from *V. tortilis* from the two sites with spider species sampled from five tree species in the Savanna Biome at Nylsvley Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) several species were repeatedly sampled. The plant dwellers include *Hamataliwa kulczynskii* (Fig. 17), *Philodromus guineensis* (Fig. 19), *Afraflacilla altera* (Fig. 20), *Baryphas ahenus* (Fig. 21), *Tmarus africanus* (Fig. 33) and *Tmarus cameliformis* (Fig. 34).

However there are numerous species that differ. This correspond with the findings of Korenko *et al.* (2011) who found differences in spider assemblage in different tree species within the mixed forest of Central Europe.

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Araneidae *Argiope australis*

Araneidae *Caerostris corticosa*

Araneidae *Cyphalonotus larvatus*

Gasteracantha versicolor

Araneidae *Isoxya tabulata*

Araneidae *Neoscona subfusca*

Araneidae *Neoscona triangula*

Eresidae *Stegodyphus dumicola*

Cheiracanthiidae *Cheiracanthium africanum*

Cheiracanthium vansoni

Clubionidae *Clubiona africana*

Hersiliidae *Hersilia sericea*

Oxyopidae *Hamataliwa kulczynskii*

Philodromidae *Philodromus browningi*

Philodromidae *Philodromus guineensis*

Salticidae *Afraflacilla altera*

Salticidae *Baryphas ahenus*

Salticidae *Myrmarachne ichneumon*

Figures 5–22. Web dwellers (5-12) and free-living plant dwellers (13-22) sampled from *Vachellia xanthophloea* from Dendron and Pongola. Credits: Peter Webb.

Salticidae *Portia schultzi*

Salticidae *Thyene inflata*

Salticidae *Thyene natalii*

Salticidae *Tusitala barbata*

Thomisidae *Heriades crassispinus*

Thomisidae *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*

Thomisidae *Simorcus cotti*

Thomisidae *Synema decens*

Thomisidae *Synema imitatrix*

Thomisidae *Thomisus scrupeus*

Thomisidae *Tmarus africanus*

Thomisidae *Tmarus camelformis*

Thomisidae *Tmarus comellinii*

Thomisidae *Tmarus longicaudatus*

Figures 23–36. Free-living plant dwelling spiders sampled from *Vachellia xanthophloea* from Dendron and Pongola. Credits: Peter Webb except 36. Stefan Foord.

TABLE 3: Spider species and their guilds (WB web dweller; FPD free living plant dwellers) sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* during surveys at the farm Vergeval district Ngotshe near Pongola (P) and the farm Amsterdam, Dendron (D).).

SPECIES	GUILD	P	D	SPECIES	GUILD	P	D
1. ARANEIDAE				9. PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	WB	1	0	<i>Hamataliwa rufocaligata</i> Simon, 1898 (Fig. 37)	FPD	0	1
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805) (Fig. 5)	WB	1	1	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	FPD	1	0
<i>Argiope flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	WB	1	0	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	FPD	1	0
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	WB	1	0	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris corticosa</i> Pocock, 1902 (Fig. 6)	WB	1	1	<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	WB	1	0	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris vicina</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	WB	1	0	10. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	WB	1	0	<i>Afraflacilla altera</i> (Wesolowska, 2000) (Fig. 20)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 7)	WB	1	1	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 21)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	WB	0	1	<i>Dendryphantes hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	FPD	1	0
<i>Gasteracantha milvoides</i> Butler, 1873	WB	1	0	<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	FPD	0	1
<i>Gasteracantha versicolor</i> (Walckenaer, 1841) (Fig. 8)	WB	1	1	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1886	FPD	1	0
<i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	WB	1	0	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	FPD	0	1
<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	WB	1	0	<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	FPD	1	0
<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859) (Fig. 9)	WB	1	1	<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	FPD	1	0
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	WB	1	1	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	WB	1	0	<i>Langona bisecta</i> Lawrence, 1927	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	WB	1	0	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837) (Fig. 10)	WB	1	1	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864) (Fig. 11)	WB	1	1	<i>Menemerus meridionalis</i> Wesolowska, 1999	FPD	0	1
<i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	WB	0	1	<i>Mogrus albogularis</i> Simon, 1901	FPD	0	1
<i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930)	WB	1	0	<i>Myrmarachne ichneumon</i> (Simon, 1886) (Fig. 22)	FPD	1	1
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	WB	0	1	<i>Myrmarachne lulengana</i> Roewer, 1965	FPD	1	0
<i>Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis</i> (Vinson, 1863)	WB	1	0	<i>Parajotus obscurolfemoratus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	FPD	0	1
2. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878 (Fig. 23)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921 (Fig. 13)	FPD	1	1	<i>Rhene machadoi</i> Berland & Millot, 1941	FPD	0	1
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	FPD	1	0	<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	FPD	0	1
<i>Cheiracanthium vansoni</i> Lawrence, 1936 (Fig. 14)	FPD	1	1	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886)	FPD	1	0
<i>Cheiramiona paradisis</i> Lotz, 2003	FPD	1	0	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873) (Fig. 24)	FPD	1	1
3. CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 25)	FPD	1	1
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921 (Fig. 15)	FPD	1	1	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	FPD	1	0
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	FPD	0	1	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902 (Fig. 26)	FPD	1	1
<i>Clubiona pongolensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	FPD	1	0	11. SELENOPIIDAE			
4. DEINOPIIDAE				<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	FPD	1	0
<i>Asianopsis cylindrica</i> (Pocock, 1898)	WB	1	0	<i>Selenops kruegeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	FPD	0	1
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	WB	1	0	12. SPARASSIDAE			
5. ERESIDAE				<i>Olios chelifera</i> Lawrence, 1937	FPD	1	0
<i>Gandanameno fumosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	WB	0	1	<i>Palystes leroyorum</i> Croeser, 1996	FPD	0	1
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 12)	WB	1	1	13. TETRAGNATHIDAE			
6. HERSILIIDAE				<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	WB	1	0
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 16)	FPD	1	1	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	WB	0	1
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	FPD	1	0				
7. MIMETIDAE							
<i>Mimetus cornutus</i> Lawrence, 1947	FPD	1	0				
8. OXYOPIIDAE							
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915) (Fig. 17)	FPD	1	1				

SPECIES	GUILD	P	D
14. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	WB	1	0
<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	WB	1	0
<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	WB	0	1
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	WB	0	1
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	WB	1	0
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	WB	1	0
15. THOMISIDAE			
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	FPD	1	1
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942 (Fig. 27)	FPD	1	1
<i>Heriaeus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1895	FPD	0	1
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 28)	FPD	1	1
<i>Mystaria savannensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	FPD	0	1
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	FPD	1	1
<i>Pherecydes carinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	FPD	1	0
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	FPD	1	0
<i>Pherecydes zebra</i> Lawrence, 1927	FPD	0	1
<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoi</i> Lessert, 1933	FPD	1	0
<i>Simorcus cotti</i> Lessert, 1936 (Fig. 29)	FPD	1	1
<i>Sylligma ndumi</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2011	FPD	1	0
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878) (Fig. 30)	FPD	1	1
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 31)	FPD	1	1
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880 (Fig. 38)	FPD	1	0
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	FPD	0	1
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886) (Fig. 32)	FPD	1	1
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	FPD	0	1
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919 (Fig. 33)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 34)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989 (Fig. 35)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	FPD	1	0
<i>Tmarus longicaudatus</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 36)	FPD	1	1
16. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Hyptiotes akermani</i> Wiehle, 1964	WD	1	0
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	WD	0	1
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	WD	0	1
17. ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Thaumastochilus termitomimus</i> Jocqué, 1994	FPD	1	0
TOTAL		79	68

Hamataliwa rufocaligata from Dendron (Stefan Foord)

Thomisus blandus from Pongola (Peter Webb)